

D6.6

OpenAIRE Publisher Dashboard Service

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Abstract	<p>The OpenAIRE Publisher Dashboard, delivered in the context of the CRAFT-OA project and integrated into the OpenAIRE MONITOR platform, offers a dedicated environment to Diamond Open Access publishers for understanding, monitoring, and communicating their publishing activity. Powered by the OpenAIRE Graph, one of the largest openly available interconnected collections of scholarly records, the Publisher Dashboard brings into one place publication data, funding links, FAIR-related attributes, impact information, and interconnections with datasets and software to form a coherent analytical view of journal and publisher outputs.</p> <p>During the reporting period, the service was designed, implemented, and validated through pilots with HRČAK and Milano University Press, whose feedback shaped the indicators and the visual presentation. The service now features a multi-level structure linking publisher-level to journal-level dashboards, allowing for broad overviews as well as detailed analysis. The resultant service reinforces evidence-based reporting for Diamond OA publishers and supplies metrics relevant to formulating their value proposition in contributing to Open Science while supporting a more transparent, trustworthy, and rewarding scholarly communication ecosystem. Further development and alignment with the European Diamond Capacity Hub (EDCH) will support wider adoption and long-term sustainability.</p>

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Disclaimer

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List of Acronyms

CC	Creative Commons (CC)
DIAMAS	Developing Institutional Open Access Publishing Models to Advance Scholarly Communication
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EC	European Commission
EDCH	European Diamond Capacity Hub
EIFL	Electronic Information for Libraries
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
FoS	Field of Science
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HRČAK	Portal of Croatian scientific and professional journals
IP	Internet Protocol
IPSP	Institutional Publishing Service Provider
JATS XML	Journal Article Tag Suite XML
OA	Open Access

OJS	Open Journal Systems
OpenAIRE	Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe
OPERAS	Open Access in the European Area through Scholarly Communication
ORCID	Open Researcher and Contributor ID
PID	Persistent Identifier
PKP	Public Knowledge Project
RFO	Research Funding Organisation
ROR	Research Organization Registry
RPO	Research Performing Organisation
WP	Work Package
XML	Extensible Markup Language

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1 Executive Summary

The Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe (OpenAIRE) Publisher Dashboard is a monitoring and analytics service developed within CRAFT-OA to help Diamond Open Access (OA) publishers gain a clearer picture of their outputs and demonstrate the value of their publishing work. Integrated into the OpenAIRE MONITOR platform¹ and powered by the OpenAIRE Graph², the Dashboard provides transparent, community-driven indicators that help institutional and scholar-led publishers evaluate their journals' reach and openness. It draws on data already available in the OpenAIRE Graph, where publishers and journals are aggregated and harmonised through OpenAIRE's established workflows. Compatibility with the OpenAIRE Guidelines³ (across supported versions) and use of tools such as the OpenAIRE Open Journal Systems (OJS) Plugin⁴ ensure that publisher data can be correctly exposed so that they are successfully aggregated, and incorporated into the Graph. Further development of the Publisher Dashboard will be driven by OpenAIRE, guided by feedback from participating publishers and the wider community.

¹ <https://monitor.openaire.eu>

² <https://graph.openaire.eu>

³ <https://guidelines.openaire.eu/en/latest/literature/index.html>

⁴ Gomola, R., Dvořáková, M., & Růžička, M. (2024). CRAFT-OA Deliverable 6.1_OJS Connector for OpenAIRE Research Graph (Draft). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12633203>

2 Objectives

The objective of Task 6.2 was to create a dedicated, interactive platform for Diamond Open Access (OA) publishers and journal editors to monitor and evaluate their performance and scholarly production. The Dashboard provides them, through a set of curated, community-driven indicators, with a consolidated and transparent view of their publishing activities and impact. It empowers publishers to showcase their contribution to Open Science, benchmark performance against peers, and identify areas for improvement. The Dashboard and its indicators remain dynamic, continuously refined through collaboration with the community and expert evaluation.

3 Description of Work Performed

The development of the Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe (OpenAIRE) Publisher Dashboard focused on the design, technical integration of a user-friendly, interactive environment incorporated into the OpenAIRE MONITOR platform. The OpenAIRE Graph serves as the data backbone for the OpenAIRE Publisher Dashboard, providing consolidated, well-structured and interconnected metadata for the research outputs of publishers and journals. By aggregating records from approximately 150,000 data sources worldwide - including repositories, journal platforms, and aggregators - and applying automated enrichment, linking, and metadata quality checks, the OpenAIRE Graph - one of the largest open collections of scholarly records worldwide supporting the adoption of Open Science practices - provides the foundation, the data backbone, on which the Publisher Dashboard operates.

A first set of indicators was designed and implemented, covering aspects such as scholarly production, funding links, licensing, metadata completeness, and OA uptake (Figure 1). These indicators were developed to provide Diamond OA publishers with a clear overview of their performance and alignment with Open Science practices. The compatibility with the OpenAIRE Guidelines were referenced as prerequisites for journals and publishers to ensure that their metadata can be properly harvested, aggregated, and visualised.

Figure 1: OpenAIRE Publisher Dashboard

An important new component introduced in the OpenAIRE Publisher Dashboard is the Multi-Level Dashboard Structure (Figure 2), which allows the Publisher Dashboard to operate as an overarching view encompassing individual dashboards for Diamond OA journals. Each journal dashboard functions as a “leaf” view under the publisher’s profile, displaying detailed indicators and metrics for that specific journal. This hierarchical structure facilitates both high-level overviews at the publisher level and granular insights at the journal level, promoting transparency and comparability across the Diamond OA ecosystem.

Sort by
Alphabetically As...Results per page
10

10

Figure 2: OpenAIRE Publisher Dashboard - List of Journals

The first pilot and review were conducted under Milestone MS16, with feedback from SRCE⁵ leading to improvements in indicator interpretation and visual presentation. The pilot phase included institutional publishers from HRČAK and the Milano University Press from University of Milan that contributed to validating the service in real-world conditions. The screenshots presented in this deliverable are taken from the public dashboard of the Croatian Academy of Sciences and Arts on HRČAK⁶, reflecting the outcomes of this pilot implementation.

The work concluded with a validation of the functional prototype and the establishment of an ongoing collaboration model through which the OpenAIRE Publisher Dashboard will continue to evolve, incorporating continuous feedback and refinements from OpenAIRE experts, pilots, and community stakeholders.

⁵ University of Zagreb University Computing Centre (SRCE) develops and maintains HRČAK.

⁶ <https://monitor.openaire.eu/dashboard/croatian-academy-of-sciences-and-arts>

4 Results and Key Outcomes

The task resulted in the deployment of a production-level OpenAIRE Publisher Dashboard service, integrated within the OpenAIRE ecosystem and fully aligned with the MONITOR platform. This service consolidates publisher-level and journal-level metrics that go beyond simple publication counts, offering comprehensive insights on the monitoring of publishing activity and assisting Diamond OA Publishers in building credibility, strengthening trust with stakeholders, and relying on data-driven foundations for sustainability, funding, and policy integration.

Following the evaluation under Milestone MS16, the indicators were revised and expanded to cover new dimensions, such as Linked Data relationships (e.g., links between publications, datasets, and software). The refinement of indicators improved both the analytical depth and interpretability of results, ensuring that publishers can better monitor and communicate their contribution to Open Science.

The production release incorporates a multi-level dashboard view connecting publisher dashboards with their associated journal dashboards, enhancing usability and transparency. The OpenAIRE Publisher Dashboard will also strengthen the collaboration among OpenAIRE, CRAFT-OA partners, and Diamond publishers, formalising a co-design process that supports continuous improvement through community engagement and expert feedback.

Search OpenAIRE Monitor Dashboards 🔍

Filters [Clear All](#)

Type [Clear](#)

- Funders (13)
- Research Initiatives (26)
- Research Institutions (70)
- Publishers (7)

Access Level

- Public (0)
- Restricted (7)

7 Dashboards Sort by Access Level ▾

Publishers x

Croatian Academy of Sciences and Arts

Creation Date: 22-07-2024
Type: Publisher

Restricted

Medicinska naklada

Creation Date: 22-07-2024
Type: Publisher

Restricted

Milano University Press

Creation Date: 09-04-2025
Type: Publisher

Restricted

The Miroslav Krleža Institute of Lexicography

Creation Date: 11-09-2025
Type: Publisher

Restricted

University of Zadar - Publisher

Creation Date: 11-09-2025
Type: Publisher

Restricted

University of Zagreb Faculty of Food Technology and Biote...

Creation Date: 15-09-2025
Type: Publisher

Restricted

University of Zagreb Faculty of Humanities and Social Scien...

Creation Date: 15-09-2025
Type: Publisher

Restricted

Figure 3: List of Publisher Dashboards currently available in the platform

5 Impact and Added Value

The OpenAIRE Publisher Dashboard increases the visibility and discoverability of Diamond OA publishers and journals within the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) by leveraging the OpenAIRE Graph as a central aggregation and harmonisation layer. Through this integration, metadata from participating publishers are enriched with additional information and connected to related research entities such as funders, projects, datasets, software, and organisations. This helps ensure that publishers' outputs are represented in a consistent and well-structured manner across EOSC services and other aggregators.

Furthermore, the Dashboard supports exposure through multiple visibility channels:

- Inclusion in the OpenAIRE Graph, which feeds the EOSC EU NODE Resource Hub⁷, ensuring discoverability across European Open Science infrastructures.
- Metadata enrichment via the OpenAIRE Broker service⁸, which supplies additional Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) (e.g. Open Researcher and Contributor ID (ORCID⁹), Digital Object Identifier (DOI¹⁰), Research Organization Registry (ROR¹¹)), OA versions, project links, and classification subjects, improving findability in external indexes.
- Standardisation through OpenAIRE Guidelines v4.0¹² and Journal Article Tag Suits Extensible Markup Language (JATS XML¹³), which guarantees metadata compatibility with repositories, aggregators, and indexing services.
- Transparent indicators and reporting dashboards, allowing publishers to communicate their visibility, reach, and Open Science alignment to funders, institutions, and the broader community.

Together, these components make Diamond OA publishers more visible, interoperable, and integrated within the European Open Science ecosystem, increasing their recognition and discoverability on both institutional and global levels.

The OpenAIRE Publisher Dashboard supports transparency, quality assurance, and data-driven decision-making for the Diamond OA community. It provides evidence-based indicators for the publishing activity, sustainability planning, policy monitoring, and funding evaluation, reinforcing OpenAIRE's role as a technical facilitator for Diamond OA and contributing to the European Open Science landscape. The Dashboard remains adaptive and evolving, with indicators refined and expanded through community collaboration and expert review.

⁷ <https://open-science-cloud.ec.europa.eu>

⁸ <https://catalogue.openaire.eu/service/openaire.broker/overview>

⁹ <https://orcid.org>

¹⁰ <https://www.doi.org>

¹¹ <https://ror.org>

¹² <https://openaire-guidelines-for-literature-repository-managers.readthedocs.io/en/v4.0.0/>

¹³ <https://jats.nlm.nih.gov>

In addition, the Multi-Level Dashboard Structure demonstrated its re-usability by being incorporated in MONITOR Dashboard for Research Initiatives, in particular for University Alliances, which can benefit from an aggregated MONITOR dashboard for the whole alliance and related institutional dashboards, one for each university member of the alliance. The work carried out in CRAFT-OA is having therefore an impact not only in the Diamond OA community, but to the wider OA and Open Science community, where universities play a fundamental role toward a sustainable digital commons of knowledge.

6 Indicator Themes and Descriptions

The Publisher Dashboard organises its analytical dimensions into a series of thematic sections, each designed to capture a specific aspect of Diamond OA publishing activity and performance. Table 1 provides detailed information about the current indicators and their breakdowns in these thematic sections.

Scholarly Output

Publications

This subsection reports the total scholarly output published by a given Diamond OA Publisher. Indicators include the number and distribution of publications, their evolution over time, and classification by journal, Field of Science (FoS), and country. These metrics illustrate the scale and diversity of publishing activity across the Diamond OA landscape.

Funding

This subsection presents indicators on project participation and grant-supported publications within Diamond OA journals. It shows how research funding contributes to the scholarly production published by institutional and community-led publishers, linking outputs to funders and projects harvested through the OpenAIRE Graph. These indicators emphasise the role of publicly funded research in sustaining Diamond OA publishing. Funding information is integrated in the OpenAIRE Graph in three ways: (i) the link to the funding project is available in the input metadata record; (ii) the funding project or funder is extracted by the OpenAIRE full-text mining algorithm; (iii) the link to the funding project is added by users with the Link functionality available in the OpenAIRE portals.

FAIR

This subsection measures the degree to which publications adhere to FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) principles through the presence of persistent identifiers, open licences, metadata completeness, and access conditions. It highlights publishers' commitment to high-quality metadata and research transparency.

Linked Data

This subsection focuses on relational aspects of scholarly publishing, showing how publications connect to other research entities such as datasets, software, funders, and institutions. Indicators demonstrate the richness of interlinking within the scholarly ecosystem and the contribution of Diamond OA publishers to a connected and interoperable research environment.

Impact

The Impact section provides evidence of the reach, frequency and influence of Diamond OA publications. It uses citation and usage-based indicators derived from OpenAIRE's integrated data sources to assess how these journals contribute to scholarly communication and knowledge dissemination.

Citations

This subsection presents citation-based indicators reflecting how often Diamond OA publications are cited in other research outputs. It includes citation counts, trends over time, and cross-journal comparisons, illustrating the scientific influence and recognition of the journals' published work.

Downloads

This subsection reports on usage-based indicators, measuring the number of downloads and accesses of Diamond OA publications across repositories and publishing platforms. It provides an early indicator of engagement and uptake, complementing citation data and helping publishers monitor the reach and frequency of their content. The downloads displayed in the dashboard are sourced from the OpenAIRE UsageCounts service, whose backend is based on Matomo analytics. By default, Matomo excludes known bots and crawlers from usage statistics by maintaining a community-contributed list of referrer spammers, helping ensure that reported usage reflects human-driven interactions as accurately as possible. The Usage Counts service collects and provides statistics on research uptake without identifying individual users. The data is processed, anonymised (anonymisation of Internet Protocol (IP-)addresses) and aggregated to protect the privacy of the individuals using the service. The service acts as a data processor, handling usage data in a way that is consistent with General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) requirements and user privacy expectations.

Table 1 provides an overview of the current indicators and their breakdown across these thematic sections; these indicators represent the present set and may be updated or expanded as the service evolves.

Scholarly Production	
Publications	
Publications	Total Over time Fields of Science (level 1) Fields of Science (level 2)
Publications also found in a Repository	Total Country
Top Journals Top Research Performing Organisations (RPOs) Top Research Funding Organisations (RFOs)	Number of publications
Top Repositories	Number of deposited publications
Funding	
Project Participations	Funder Over time
European Commission (EC) Project Participations	FP, over time
Grant-supported publications	Funder Over time Fields of Science (level 1) Fields of Science (level 2)
FAIR	
Publications	License type With/without Creative Commons (CC) license With/without ORCID iD PID type
Linked Data	
Publications	Total Linked to Datasets Supplemented by a Dataset Linked to Software Supplemented by a Software
Publications linked to Datasets/Software	Over time Fields of Science (level 1) Fields of Science (level 2)

Top Journals Top RPOs Top RFOs	Number of publications linked to datasets Number of publications linked to software
Impact	
Citations	
Total Citations	Total Over time (year of publication) by Country Fields of Science (levels 1 & 2)
Average Citations per Publication	Over time (year of publication) by Country Fields of Science (levels 1 & 2)
Top Journals Top RPOs	Total citations Average Citations
Downloads	
Total Downloads	Total Over time (year of publication) Over time (year of download) With/Without Abstract Fields of Science (levels 1 & 2)
Top Journals Top RPOs	Total downloads Average downloads

Table 1: Overview of the current indicators and their thematic breakdown

7 Sustainability and Future Plans

Given that other CRAFT-OA deliverables under Work Package (WP) 7 already address service sustainability and long-term governance in detail, this section is kept concise. Further information on sustainability planning and maintenance is provided in Deliverable D7.7, which describes these aspects meticulously.

The Publisher Dashboard will continue to be offered as part of the OpenAIRE MONITOR service family, with ongoing maintenance and improvements introduced through regular development cycles. Future enhancements include new collaboration and benchmarking indicators aligned with institutional scholarly publishing activity, expanded usage analytics, and a wider group of participants (pilots/early adopters). Closer coordination and co-branding with the European Diamond Capacity Hub (EDCH) will support a consistent approach across Diamond OA community, particularly in relation to operational alignment, and long-term sustainability.

To increase uptake, an essential condition for the dashboard to deliver meaningful impact, OpenAIRE and CRAFT-OA communication team has already initiated concrete actions. In mid and end 2025, two Open Calls were launched targeting Institutional Publishing Service Providers (IPSPs) from the Developing Institutional Open Access Publishing Models to Advance Scholarly Communication (DIAMAS) project. These calls aim to broaden participation, diversify use cases, and encourage Diamond OA publishers to engage with the Publisher dashboard as part of a wider ecosystem of capacity-building support coordinated by the EDCH and OpenAIRE. Follow-up activities will focus on hands-on onboarding and support to Diamond OA publishers to improve the completeness and accuracy of their metadata records, ensuring that dashboards generate reliable and actionable insights.

8 Conclusion

The development of the OpenAIRE Publisher Dashboard within CRAFT-OA highlights the value of providing Diamond OA publishers with a dedicated service that helps them understand and present their publishing activity. The pilots with HRČAK and Milano University Press confirmed both the relevance of the indicators and the practical benefits of a shared analytical tool, while also highlighting the importance of improving metadata quality to enhance the quality of the output of the Publisher Dashboard. The Dashboard has made a significant step on providing a stable basis for evidence-based monitoring and for strengthening the position of Diamond OA publishers within the broader Open Science landscape.

The Publisher Dashboard will continue to be offered as part of the OpenAIRE MONITOR service family, with ongoing enhancements and closer coordination with the EDCH. This will support coherence across Diamond OA services and encourage wider uptake among publishers, in collaboration with SRCE/HRČAK, Masaryk University, Public Knowledge Projects (PKP), Open Access in the European Area through Scholarly Communication (OPERAS), EIFL and the broader community.

9 References

9.1 List of References

- Gomola, R., Dvořáková, M., & Růžička, M. (2024). CRAFT-OA Deliverable 6.1_OJS Connector for OpenAIRE Research Graph (Draft). Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12633203>

9.2 List of Websites

- <https://monitor.openaire.eu>
 - <https://monitor.openaire.eu/dashboards.html>
 - <https://monitor.openaire.eu/dashboard/croatian-academy-of-sciences-and-arts>
- <https://graph.openaire.eu>
- <https://guidelines.openaire.eu/en/latest/literature/index.html>
 - <https://openaire-guidelines-for-literature-repository-managers.readthedocs.io/en/v4.0.0>
- <https://open-science-cloud.ec.europa.eu>
- <https://catalogue.openaire.eu/service/openaire.broker/overview>
- <https://jats.nlm.nih.gov>
- <https://orcid.org>
- <https://www.doi.org>
- <https://ror.org>

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